

ISic1261

I.Sicily inscription 1261

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140749

1. [— —]NAN [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. ΠΙΕ[—]ΟΝΙΕ[—]ΥΝΟΑ[— — — —] {²⁷εὐνο[ί]α [ς ἔνεκα] }²⁷
3. [— —]ΑΣΚΑΙΤΑ[— —]ΜΑΥΥΟ [— —]
4. [— —]ΙΟΝΚ[— —] Συρακόσ[ι]ον
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492867

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PHI 140749

Bibliography

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